

Codebook for the analysis of evidence use in the public discourse on pesticides in Switzerland

Ueli Reber ^{1,*}

ORCID: 0000-0001-8036-4493

Karin Ingold ^{1,2}

ORCID: 0000-0001-8166-1780

Christian Stamm ¹

ORCID: 0000-0001-5888-6535

¹ Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag), Dübendorf, Switzerland

² University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland

* Corresponding author: ueli.reber@eawag.ch

Funding: The codebook was created in the context of the Sinergia project [“Evidence-based transformation in pesticide governance”](#) (TRAPEGO), work package 2, which is funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF, project number 193762)

Acknowledgments: Sincere thanks for the thorough testing and critical discussion of the codebook go to the coders Mirjam Grünholz, Laura Jäggi, Yvan Jutzi, and Michael Zysset. Thanks also to our colleagues Benjamin Hofmann and Milena Wiget for their valuable feedback on the codebook as well as Beatrice Eugster and Hannah Schmid-Petri for their expert advice on the coding process.

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Cite as: Reber, U., Ingold, K., & Stamm, C. (2023). *Codebook for the analysis of evidence use in the public discourse on pesticides in Switzerland*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8124824>

This version: 2023-07-07

1 Introduction

This codebook was developed and used to analyse evidence use in the public discourse on pesticides in Switzerland. This includes media articles, articles of trade magazines, and political documents (e.g., speeches, acts, consultations).

1.1 Purpose and scope

The public discourse on pesticide use revolves around questions about risks related to either pesticide use or the reduction of pesticide use. In this codebook, we refer to such questions as **pesticide problems**. Different actors formulate not only different pesticide problems (e.g., pesticides cause health problems, abandoning pesticides results in yield losses), but also different **solutions** to those problems (e.g., ban of certain pesticides, subsidies for resistant varieties). The process of selecting certain problem definitions and solutions as well as highlighting them is commonly referred to as **framing** (Entman, 1993).

In order to make a particular frame more plausible (e.g., to prove the validity of a claim), actors may use evidence. We define **evidence use** as “any reference to factual data or information as proof that a certain belief or proposition [i.e., claim] is true or valid” (Yanovitzky & Weber, 2020, p. 71; see also Majone, 1989, p. 48). By factual, we mean based on either systematic research/analysis or unsystematic research, but based on actual, (potentially) verifiable situations (i.e., not fictional thought experiments). This definition includes both research and non-research evidence (e.g., personal experience, media reports). This means that evidence, as we understand it, is used deliberately and for different purposes and motives (Boswell, 2008; Majone, 1989).

The main unit of analysis of the codebook are **evidence-frame sequences**. Evidence-frame sequences form a two-level structure, with the evidence sequences at the first level and the frame sequences as the second one. Figure 1 illustrates this structure. An **evidence sequence** thereby consists of a claim about risks of (reducing) pesticide use and a reference to factual data or information, while the **frame sequence** consists of the problem definition and solution highlighted by the **speaker**. Linking the three elements to form an evidence-frame sequence, the codebook is designed to collect information (1) on the type of evidence used (*evidence sequence attributes*), (2) on the frame communicated by the speaker (*frame sequence attributes*), and (3) on the speaker (*actor attributes*). In addition, (4) the codebook includes variables needed to collect document level attributes (*document attributes*).

Figure 1. Coding structure.

1.2 Sample documents

The codebook is intended to code Swiss mass media articles, trade media articles, and policy documents addressing risks of either pesticide use or the reduction of their use published between 2010 and 2022. In the case of media, we code all editorial articles (including opinion/comments, guest posts, and letters to the editor). Excluded are advertisements, event notes, paid posts, press releases, and teasers (e.g., on the front page). Boxes with additional information (e.g., explanations of terms) are also excluded.

By pesticides we mean chemical substances or plant protection products (PPP), including herbicides, fungicides and insecticides. Documents become part of the sample if one of the following search terms in English or their equivalent in German or French is mentioned at least once in the document: *pesticide*, *insecticide*, *herbicide*, *fungicide*, *plant protection product*.

Although the codebook was developed for the Swiss context (i.e., all language regions), the examples included make it primarily suitable for coding documents written in German as we used machine translation services to translate French documents into German to facilitate the coding process.

1.3 Coding procedure

For each document, we first collect document level attributes. If the document does not contain a relevant evidence-frame sequence, the coding process terminates at this point. Otherwise, the coding of the document continues with the relevant evidence-frame sequence(s). For each evidence-frame sequence, we code evidence sequence attributes and frame sequence attributes before possibly moving on to the next evidence-frame sequence. Figure 2 provides a graphical overview of the coding procedure.

Figure 2. Coding procedure.

From a coder perspective, coding of a documents involves the following steps:

- (1) Take a document from the folder dedicated to the coder.
- (2) For PDFs with multiple articles in the same document (e.g., BauernZeitung, die Grüne): identify the article that contains the keyword(s).
- (3) For mass/trade media: Decide if the article is an editorial article and therefore relevant for coding.
- (4) If the article is not an editorial article: place the document in the archive folder. If the article is an editorial article: proceed with the coding.
- (5) Read the whole document/article (hereinafter simply referred to as document).
- (6) Decide if the document includes at least one relevant evidence-frame sequence of a speaker communicating a relevant frame (see section 3 below for details).
- (7) If the document includes no relevant evidence sequence: code the document's exclusion using the DOC_VARS coding form and place the document in the designated archive folder. If the document includes a relevant evidence-frame sequence: proceed with the coding.
- (8) Code document level attributes using the DOC_VARS coding form.
- (9) Code the evidence-frame sequence using the ES/FS/ACT_VARS coding forms.
- (10) If the document includes additional evidence sequences: repeat step 9 for each of them.
- (11) Place the document in the archive folder.

1.4 *General rules*

There are some general rules to keep in mind when coding (Schmid-Petri et al., 2013):

- Ambiguities are part of the coding process. They should not be resolved by random coding, but should always be noted and discussed at the next coder meeting or bilaterally with the supervisor.
- Coding should be based on the written text. Interpretations that go beyond the coding instructions in this codebook are to be avoided.
- Specific categories have priority over general categories. This means that whenever possible, coders should choose specific subcategories rather than the broader meta categories, e.g., Guy Parmelin should be coded as "government" rather than "political actor".

2 Document attributes

2.1 Document attributes supplied by database

Variables that are available from the document database:

Document ID [DOC_ID, txt]¹

The document ID follows the pattern X-Y (e.g., 1824-13-45232), where X indicates the source and Y is a sequentially generated number among the documents from that source.

Coder ID [CODER_ID, num]

1	Laura
2	Michael
3	Mirjam
4	Yvan
5	Ueli

Source name [SOURCE_NAME, txt]

Publication date year [DATE_Y, num]

Publication date month [DATE_M, num]

Publication date day [DATE_D, num]

Document language [DOC_LANG, num]

1	German
2	French

FILTER: Parliamentary acts

Type of parliamentary act [PARL_TYPE, num]

1	Parlamentarische Initiative
2	Standesinitiative
3	Motion
4	Postulat
5	Interpellation
6	Anfrage
7	Frage (Fragestunde)

1 Meaning of abbreviations in square brackets: num = numeric variable, txt = text/string variable, man = mandatory variable. Name of the variable in capital letters.

8	Geschäft des Parlaments
9	Geschäft des Bundesrates

END OF FILTER: All cases

2.2 Document attributes to code (Coding form: DOC_VARS)

The following variables must be coded manually using the appropriate coding form.

Document ID [DOC_ID, txt, man]

Must be taken from the file name. The ID in the file name is preceded by a four-digit number. This number is randomly generated during the sampling process and ensures that the documents are coded in random order. The number is not part of the DOC_ID and must be ignored, e.g., 13-4523 from the file name 2314-13-4523.pdf.

In cases where a document is in the same file with several others (entire issues of the BauernZeitung, Die Grüne), the file name is supplemented by the page number on which the particular article can be found. The page information is not part of the DOC_ID and must therefore not be coded (e.g. DOC_ID 13-11415 on page 11 of file 7323-13-11415-p11.pdf).

In these cases (entire issues of the BauernZeitung, Die Grüne), for technical reasons, the DOC_ID always refers to the entire page and not a specific article. If several articles on the particular page contain the search terms, we code the most prominent one.

Figure 3. Structure of document name.

FILTER: multi-page articles

Document IDs for other pages [DOC_ID_OTH, txt]

In some cases, articles span multiple pages of a PDF (e.g., Die Grüne). We always code the entire article, i.e. the whole article must be considered, not just the landing page. However, since the DOC_ID in these cases only refers to the page specified in the document name, the DOC_IDs of the other pages must be coded to prevent resampling of the article.

Since the second part of the DOC_ID are running numbers, the DOC_ID of the previous/following pages can be inferred (-1 for the previous and +1 for the following page). For example, the article in document 7323-13-11415-p11.pdf spans three pages, with the first page being p.10 and the last p.12, the DOC_ID of the document is 13-11415, while there would be two DOC_ID_OTH: 13-11414, 13-11416.

Note all DOC_IDs of the other documents as comma separated list.

END OF FILTER: All cases

FILTER: For media documents

Type of article [ART_TYPE, num]

(Schmid-Petri et al., 2013; Waldherr et al., 2015)

Please code the article type to which the media document can be attributed.

1	News / report A factual piece of information that relates to a specific event, topic, or actor. Characteristics: not subjectively tinged; most important information at the beginning; reporting is usually triggered by a recent event.
2	Editorial (“Leitartikel”) The opinion of the editorial team on an issue, i.e. it does not reflect the opinion of a single person or editor, but that of the media outlet/the majority of the editorial team. This category is only coded if the media outlet marks an article as editorial.
3	Commentary / opinion piece Opinionated, commenting text, focusing on the formation of opinion. Characteristics: interpretation and evaluation of current events; factual opinion style or irony/satire.
4	Interview Dialogue between two or more persons, the change of speaker is identified as such in the article. Short interview statements within a report are not an interview.
5	Reportage / feature Factual text with personal and subjective tinge, usually more comprehensive treatment of an event or a person (“Porträt”). Characteristics: often scenic introduction; own perspective as stylistic device.
6	Advice (“Ratgeberartikel”) Article providing advice for, e.g., the application of pesticides, the handling of food.
7	Letter to the editor A letter sent to a media outlet by one of its readers addressing some issue of concern, e.g., the opinion expressed in a commentary.
99	Other, unclear

END OF FILTER: All cases

Triggering event [TRIG_EVENT, num, man]

(Adam et al., 2002)

In some cases, the writing of the document was triggered by a specific event or incident. We code events explicitly mentioned in the text that are not unspecified statements (e.g., experts warn..., farmers are recently blamed for...), and for political documents, everyday political business (e.g., committee meetings, policy proposals). The triggering event can also be a historical event. To

determine whether there is a triggering event, you can ask yourself **what event/incident triggered the writing of the document?**

If more than one triggering event is mentioned, we only code the one mentioned first. If no event is mentioned (e.g., advice article with general background information), use code 0.

0	No triggering event	
10	Legislative / administrative / authority action Legislative actions (e.g., passing of laws), governmental actions (e.g., start of consultation), regulations by state executive agencies (e.g., establishing prescriptive limits for certain substances, pesticide registration, granting of emergency authorizations), also actions of police, military, and other officials (e.g., arrests, fines, security checks, official controls, inspections, moratoria on sales, shut-down of production sites) <i>For political documents:</i> We do not code events from everyday political business, e.g., committee meetings, publication of policy proposals	
20	Direct-democratic action Initiating referenda/initiative, voting on referenda/initiative, collecting signatures for referenda/initiative	
30	Protest, mobilizing event, press conference Public assemblies, marches, demonstrations, boycotts, strikes, violent protests, press conferences	
40	Meeting, conference Conventions, congresses, summits, assemblies, conferences, exhibition, fair, symposium, discussion forum, informative meeting, etc.	
50	Agricultural event Pest pressure, start of planting/harvest/sale season, crop loss, etc.	
60	(Alleged) criminal action, man-made disaster, accident Corruption, fraud, violence, intentional pollution, fish kills due to pesticides pollution, etc. also court decisions	
70	Publication	
	71	Scientific study Also announcement or start of a new study
	72	Report or survey Official reports, reports of NGOs, etc.
	73	Media Newspaper, magazine, trade magazine, radio, TV program, news agency, cinema, movie, book, website, blog, social media, online media, etc.
99	Other triggering event	

FILTER: If TRIG_EVENT ≠ 0

Triggering event scope [TRIG_EVENT_SCOPE, num]

Please code the area subject to the triggering event using the separate list of areas.

Normally, the scope of the triggering event is the country in which the event happened (tab “National”). Exceptions are supra-, inter-, or transnational events (e.g. international protests, political events in the EU), where we code the supra-, inter-, or transnational area that is subject to the event (tab “Regional”). If the area subject to the triggering event can not be inferred, use code 999 (unclear).

END OF FILTER: All cases

Centrality of pesticide use in document [PEST_CENTR, num, man]

(Sowka et al., 2011)

1	Low centrality Pesticide use is of low centrality (a peripheral aspect) when the document deals with the issue only marginally compared to other topics in the text. This means that it is only shortly mentioned in the document, i.e. only one or two sentences deal with the issue (for longer articles: less than one paragraph).
2	Medium centrality Pesticide use is of medium centrality when it is an issue next to others and dealt with (= not just mentioned) more or less extensively, but do not stand out clearly against the other issues, i.e. the topic is not prominent in the title or lead.
3	High centrality Pesticide use is of high centrality when it constitutes the main aspect or one of the main aspects of the article; it should be mentioned in the title, headline, or within the first third of the document.

END OF FILTER: All cases

3 Evidence-frame sequence attributes

To capture evidence use in the discourse on pesticides, we look at **evidence-frame sequences**. As outlined in the introduction, an evidence-sequence consists of an **evidence sequence** and a **frame sequence**.

Evidence sequence: Based on Toulmin's argument model (Toulmin, 2003), every evidence sequence consists of (1) a **claim** about risks of (reducing) pesticide use, and (2) a reference to factual data or information that serves as proof that the claim is true or valid, i.e., **evidence** (Yanovitzky & Weber, 2020). By factual, we mean information derived from either systematic research/analysis or unsystematic research/experience, but based on actual, (potentially) verifiable situations (see section 3.1 below). Every evidence sequence can be attributed to a **speaker** (see section 3.3 below). Note that the claim can be the speaker's claim (i.e., part of her/his frame), but it does not have to be (i.e., if it is the claim of the evidence source).

Speaker: Claim ← Evidence (← Source)

- *Example 1 (research evidence speaking to the problem)*: Clean drinking water can no longer be taken for granted today because agriculture pollutes groundwater with nitrate and pesticide metabolites: This is the conclusion of the Federal Office for the Environment from a long-term study published yesterday.
- *Example 2 (non-research evidence speaking to the solution)*: "The prognostic model allows us to delay initial treatments and, as a consequences, save one to two treatments," says the farmer, summarizing his experience over the past two years.
- *Example 3 (research evidence [w/ source] speaking to the problem)*: In 2020, the Environmental Protection Agency and the National Institute of Health in the USA published a comprehensive review of the available scientific literature. It concludes that 191 studies describe effects of neonicotinoids on human health and mammals. (speaker: MP)

In a first step, we code information on the evidence sequence level (*evidence sequence attributes*), such as the type of evidence used (EV_TYPE, EV_QUANT), whether evidence speaks to a problem or a proposed solution (EV_GOAL), and whether the evidence supports or contradicts the speaker's framing (EV_VAL). Furthermore, the speaker may mention the **source** of the evidence. By evidence source, we mean the actor who produced the factual data or information referred to by the speaker. If the speaker mentions an evidence source, we also collect information about that actor.

Frame sequence: An evidence sequence is part of a **speaker's framing** of the pesticide issue. By framing we mean the promotion of a particular **problem definition** along with a possible **solution** (SOL_TYPE, SOL_POS) of the problem (Entman, 2013). Thereby, a pesticide problem is a causal relationship between the **causes** (PROB_CAU) and **consequences** (PROB_CON) of (the reduction of) pesticide use (PROB_TYPE) acknowledged or denied as a risk (PROB_POS). In a second step, we are interested in this broader line or argumentation the **speaker** tries to establish (*frame sequence attributes*).

The following parts of the codebook are therefore designed to collect information on (1) the evidence used by the speaker (ES_VARS), (2) the framing conveyed by the speaker (FS_VARS), and (3) information on the actors involved, i.e. the evidence source and the speaker ACT_VARS.

To identify evidence-frame sequences in a given document, we look for evidence sequences. As mentioned above, an evidence sequence is defined by (1) a claim about risks of (reducing) pesticide use, (2) evidence, and (3) the speaker. Whenever one of the three features change (for the identification of the speaker, see section 3.3 below), we code a new evidence-frame sequence. Accordingly, there may be multiple evidence sequences for the same speaker in a document all contributing to the her/his framing, e.g., if there is one evidence sequence for the problem and one for the suggested solution. The sum of an actor's statements in a document thus aggregates to her/his framing of the pesticide issue in a given document. That is, for any speaker, we code only one frame per document (i.e., the dominant one). We disregard evidence sequences that refer exclusively to a second, marginal frame.

If a speaker uses evidence in connection with a possible solution and does not explicitly mention a pesticide problem, we infer the problem type from the context provided in the document. Also, it is permissible to code an evidence sequence if a speaker does not explicitly mention pesticides, e.g., if a speaker uses evidence to proof the challenges of organic farming and it was established before that organic farming means pesticide-reduced farming.

The following procedure applies to the identification and coding of evidence-frame sequences:

- (1) Read the whole document.
- (2) Identify all evidence sequences, i.e. references to factual data or information as proof that a certain claim about risks of (reducing) pesticide use is true or valid (see section 3.1 below).
- (3) For each evidence sequence, identify the speaker (see section 3.3 below).
- (4) Assign an evidence-frame sequence ID (EFS_ID) to each evidence sequence belonging to a relevant speaker.
- (5) For each speaker, note down the actor attributes.
- (6) For the speaker of the first evidence sequence (i.e., EFS_ID 1): note down the frame sequence attributes of the first speaker's frame sequence (see section 3.2 below).
- (7) Note down the evidence sequence attributes for the first evidence sequence as well as possible other evidence sequences by the same speaker, including the evidence source (if any).
- (8) Record the noted information (steps 6-8) using the ES/FS/ACT_VARS coding forms.
- (9) Repeat steps 7 and 8 for every speaker identified.

3.1 Evidence sequence attributes (Coding form: ES_VARS)

As mentioned above, evidence is a reference to factual data or information to prove that a particular claim is true or valid. By factual, we mean information derived from either systematic research/analysis or unsystematic research/experience, but based on real-world situations. The delimitation between factual and non-factual is not always clear-cut. Therefore, please adhere to the following rules:

- Fictional examples that are logically coherent but not based on actual observations are not coded as evidence, e.g., if someone uses the case of a fictional farmer to illustrate the effect of a policy. An exception to this are testimonies, i.e., when experts' statements are used in support of an argument. In this case, the evidence is not the fictional example, but the fact that it is formulated by an expert.
- We only code expert testimonies (i.e., statements by qualified individuals) as evidence when speaker and evidence source are not the same actor. In other words, an expert does not validate her/his own statements by her/his status as an expert alone, but must cite research results or similar.
Note: This only applies to statements by individuals, not (official) statements by organisations. So, for example, if the IARC is quoted as saying that Glyphosate does not cause cancer, we assume that the statement is based on research conducted by the organisation on this matter, even if this is not mentioned in the text.
- We do not code references to policy decisions of other countries as evidence, e.g., France recognizes Parkinson's disease as an occupational disease of farmers; Germany also supports a ban on Glyphosate. What we do code, however, are observed outcomes of policy decisions, e.g., the introduction of the professional user permit led to a decrease in pesticide sales in France
- For media documents: We only code a distinct evidence sequence for the lead of an article if both claim and evidence do not also occur in the actual text of the article.

Document ID [DOC_ID, txt, man]

The DOC_ID of the document as described in the section on document level attributes above.

Evidence-frame sequence ID [EFS_ID, txt, man]

The ID of the evidence sequence must be attributed by the coder based on the evidence sequence's position in the text as an integer number (1, 2, 3, etc.). The EFS_ID for the first evidence sequence is 1, for the second 2, for the third 3, and so on.

Important: Make sure that you use the same EFS_ID for all codings related to the same evidence-frame sequence (i.e. actors, evidence sequence). Otherwise, the coded information cannot be linked together.

Evidence sequence text [EV_TXT, txt, man]

Please copy and paste the evidence sequence from the original document as complete as possible so that it includes both the **evidence** and, if present, the **source**. Make sure to copy only complete sentences, including punctuation.

If an evidence sequence is fragmented, i.e. spread over several unconnected passages in the text, the fragments can be concatenated with [...] as separator. However, if a speaker takes distinct information/claims from the same source (e.g., evidence for a problem and a solution from the same study), code them as separate sequences of evidence.

Type of evidence: research vs. non-research [EV_TYPE, num, man]

(Yanovitzky & Weber, 2020)

For each evidence sequence, we code the type of evidence used. We thereby distinguish between **(1) research evidence** and **(2) non-research evidence**. To identify the evidence type, we consider both the evidence itself and its source. The following flowchart helps to identify the right type of evidence.

Important: also non-scientific professionals/institutions can produce research evidence, e.g., administration/state agencies, NGOs, agrochemical companies.

Figure 5. Type of evidence.

1	Research evidence Proof derived from systematic research and analysis conducted with scientific rigour and methods. This includes evidence from (1) scientific/academic studies (e.g., empirical studies, research syntheses), (2) reports, assessments, reviews, evaluations, monitoring programs, and datasets that adhere to basic scientific standards, (3) statistical facts (presumably) derived from type (1) and (2) analyses, as well as (4) statements or
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	<p>testimonies from actors other than the speaker whose expertise come from systematic research and analysis (e.g., research professionals, government specialists).</p> <p><i>e.g., drei vom Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft in Auftrag gegebene Studien kommen zum Schluss, dass die Schweizer Agrarwirtschaft punkto Wettbewerbsfähigkeit noch einiges aufzuholen hat; eine Folgeuntersuchung hat gezeigt, dass auch die Abbauprodukte dieser Pestizide weiterhin toxische Risiken bergen; zahlreiche Studien belegen, dass Neonicotinoide am Bienensterben mitschuldig sind; das ETH-Forschungsinstitut Eawag hat aufgezeigt, dass Bäche im Landwirtschaftsgebiet stark mit Herbiziden und Insektiziden belastet sind; die Forschung zeigt, dass das Risiko einer Erkrankung bei Personen steigt, die bei der Ausübung ihres Berufes giftige Produkte verwenden; "aus einem Drittel der Areale, die der Igel vor 25 Jahren noch bewohnte, hat er sich mittlerweile zurückgezogen", sagt die Wildtierbiologin; das Monitoringprogramm des BAFUs zeigt, dass die Hälfte der Lebensräume und ein Drittel der Arten bedroht sind; in der Schweiz ist der Einsatz synthetischer Pestizide in den letzten zehn Jahren um 27 Prozent zurückgegangen; auch der Bericht zur Evaluation der Zulassung von Pflanzenschutzmitteln kommt zum Schluss, dass in verschiedenen Bereichen Verbesserungspotential besteht; gemäss Merkblatt des BLW soll eine Driftreduktion von 50 bis 95 Prozent erreicht werden, schon alleine, wenn mit geringerem Druck und Injektordüsen gespritzt wird</i></p>
2	<p>Non-research evidence</p> <p>Proof derived from (1) personal experience (e.g., own farming practice), (2) casual or non-systematic observations (e.g., stakeholder feedback, situation in other countries or cases), (3) anecdotes, (4) media reports, (5) non-systematic investigations or searches, and (6) statements or testimonies from actors other than the speaker whose expertise does not come from systematic research and analysis (e.g., laypeople). This includes evidence presented as statistical facts when obtained by means other than those described above (research evidence).</p> <p><i>e.g., wie verschiedene Medienberichte gezeigt haben, werden die bereits existierenden Regulierungen oft nicht eingehalten und ungenügend kontrolliert; wie aus der Antwort des Bundesrates hervorgeht, befindet sich die Schweiz hier im Blindflug; obwohl ich schon lange im Rentenalter bin und in der Landwirtschaft gearbeitet habe, habe ich keinen Krebs und meine Freunde, die Bauern sind, auch nicht; der Imker weiss aus eigener Erfahrung, Varroa ist die Gefahr Nummer 1 für Honigbienen; mit dem Striegel habe ich einen doppelt so hohen Aufwand und die Traktor-Stunden verdoppeln sich auch; bei einem Pestizidverbot, so haben die Brüder ausgerechnet, würde aufgrund der geringeren Futterproduktion die jährliche Milchproduktion auf ihrem Hof von 320.000 kg auf 235.000 kg sinken</i></p>
99	Unclear

FILTER: If EV_TYPE = 1

Certainty of research evidence [EV_CERT, num]

In some cases the speaker points out the degree of (un)certainty of the evidence used. For research evidence, we code this assessment by the speaker. If the speaker provides no assessment, leave the variable blank.

1	Low certainty <i>e.g., die Studie gibt erste Hinweise darauf; vorläufige Befunde zeigen; Resultate zu verwandten Stoffen lassen vermuten; aus einer als Preprint veröffentlichten Studie</i>
2	High certainty <i>e.g., zahlreiche Studien belegen; in der Wissenschaft besteht Konsens darüber; konnte in verschiedenen Versuchen gezeigt werden; es ist wissenschaftlich unbestritten; wie seit langem bekannt</i>

Credibility of research evidence [EV_CRED, num]

(Schmid-Petri et al., 2013)

If either the source of research evidence (ACT_ROLE = 2) or the research evidence itself is evaluated in terms of its credibility, we code the speaker's evaluation. If the speaker provides no evaluation, leave the variable blank.

1	Low credibility <i>e.g., der gekaufte Wissenschaftler; mit ungeeigneten Methoden fabrizierte Befunde; aus fragwürdiger Quelle</i>
2	High credibility <i>e.g., die hochdekorierte Forscherin; von einem renommierten Forschungsinstitut; die weltweit angesehenste/meist zitierte Zeitschrift für Naturwissenschaften, nach eingehender Analyse</i>

END OF FILTER: All cases

Type of evidence: quantified vs. non-quantified [EV_QUANT, num, man]

Please specify whether the speaker uses quantities (i.e., numbers, statistics) as evidence.

1	Quantified evidence <i>e.g., aus einem Drittel der Areale, die der Igel vor 25 Jahren noch bewohnte, hat er sich mittlerweile zurückgezogen", sagt die Wildtierbiologin; das Monitoringprogramm des BAFUs zeigt, dass die Hälfte der Lebensräume und ein Drittel der Arten bedroht sind; in der Schweiz ist der Einsatz synthetischer Pestizide in den letzten zehn Jahren um 27 Prozent zurückgegangen; mit dem Striegel habe ich einen doppelt so hohen Aufwand und die Traktor-Stunden verdoppeln sich auch; bei einem Pestizidverbot, so haben die Brüder ausgerechnet, würde aufgrund der geringeren Futterproduktion die jährliche Milchproduktion auf ihrem Hof von 320.000 kg auf 235.000 kg sinken</i>
2	Non-quantified evidence

e.g., eine Folgeuntersuchung hat gezeigt, dass auch die Abbauprodukte dieser Pestizide weiterhin toxische Risiken bergen; zahlreiche Studien belegen, dass Neonicotinoide am Bienensterben mitschuldig sind; das ETH-Forschungsinstitut Eawag hat aufgezeigt, dass Bäche im Landwirtschaftsgebiet stark mit Herbiziden und Insektiziden belastet sind; wie verschiedene Medienberichte gezeigt haben, werden die bereits existierenden Regulierungen oft nicht eingehalten und ungenügend kontrolliert; wie aus der Antwort des Bundesrates hervorgeht, befindet sich die Schweiz hier im Blindflug; obwohl ich schon lange im Rentenalter bin und in der Landwirtschaft gearbeitet habe, habe ich keinen Krebs und meine Freunde, die Bauern sind, auch nicht; der Imker weiss aus eigener Erfahrung, Varroa ist die Gefahr Nummer 1 für Honigbienen

Goal of evidence use [EV_GOAL, num, man]

(Yanovitzky & Weber, 2020)

Evidence can speak to either a pesticide problem or a potential solution. Please specify whether the claim made in the evidence sequence is about a pesticide problem (e.g., its objective status, cause, consequence) or a solution (e.g., its effectiveness) of a pesticide problem.

Question: Is the claim of the evidence sequence about a problem or a solution?

For the specific case where a speaker uses evidence for a policy that she/he identifies as the cause of a problem and therefore rejects it – i.e., the policy is both the cause and the solution to the problem, if it is discarded – we code EV_GOAL 1 when existing policies are criticized (status quo) and EV_GOAL 2 when the speaker opposes a policy proposal.

1	Evidence speaks to a pesticide problem
2	Evidence speaks to the solution of a pesticide problem
99	Unclear

Valence of evidence use [EV_VAL, num, man]

(Yanovitzky & Weber, 2020)

Please specify the valence of the evidence sequence relative to the speakers framing, i.e., whether the evidence in the sequence supports, contradicts, or is ambivalent towards the speaker's problem definition / solution.

If a speaker's position on a pesticide problem is unclear (PROB_POS = 99), we code the valence of the evidence as unclear by default (EV_VAL = 99).

1	Evidence supports the speaker's framing
2	Evidence contradicts the speaker's framing
3	Evidence is ambivalent towards the speaker's framing
99	Unclear

3.2 Frame sequence attributes (Coding form: FS_VARS)

To identify frame sequence attributes, especially the causal link of the problem definition, you can ask the following questions:

Problem definition	<p>PROB_TYPE: Is the problem described by the speaker ultimately about pesticide use or about reducing pesticide use?</p> <p>PROB_CON: What (potential) negative consequences of [pesticide use / reducing pesticide use] are emphasized by the speaker?</p> <p>PROB_CAU: What causes (or would cause) the problematic [use of pesticides / reduction of pesticide use] according to the speaker?</p>
	<p>PROB_POS: Does the speaker acknowledge/deny the pesticide problem described, i.e., the causal relationship of causes and consequences of [pesticide use / reducing pesticide use]?</p>
Solution	<p>SOL_TYPE: What measures or actions are mentioned by the speaker as a solution to the pesticide problem?</p>
	<p>SOL_POS: Does the speaker support/oppose the described measures or actions?</p>

Document ID [DOC_ID, txt, man]

The DOC_ID of the document as described in the section on document level attributes above.

Evidence-frame sequence ID [EFS_ID, txt, man]

The ID of the evidence sequence must be attributed by the coder based on the evidence sequence's position in the text as an integer number (1, 2, 3, etc.). The EFS_ID for the first evidence sequence is 1, for the second 2, for the third 3, and so on.

If there are several evidence sequences linked to the same same frame sequence, you must code the frame attributes only once by listing the relevant EFS_IDs as comma-separated list, e.g., 1, 2, 3.

Important: Make sure that you use the same EFS_ID for all codings related to the same evidence-frame sequence (i.e. actors, evidence sequence). Otherwise, the coded information cannot be linked together.

Problem definition

Type of pesticide problem [PROB_TYPE, num, man]

Please specify the type of the pesticide problem expressed by the speaker. We distinguish between two main types of pesticide problems: **(1) problem is related to pesticide use** or **(2) problem is related to the reduction of pesticide use**. For example, if a speaker is worried about pesticide residues in food, use code 1 pesticide use. If, on the other hand, a speaker is concerned about yield losses when pesticides are prohibited, use code 2 reduction of pesticide use.

Question: Is the problem described by the speaker ultimately about pesticide use or about reducing pesticide use?

1	Problem is related to pesticide use
2	Problem is related to the reduction of pesticide use

Consequences of the pesticide problem [PROB_CON, num, man]

Please specify the consequences of the pesticide problem emphasised the most by the speaker.

Question: What (potential) negative consequences of [pesticide use / reducing pesticide use] are emphasized by the speaker?

0	No consequences mentioned
1	<p>Environmental consequences</p> <p><i>e.g., der Einsatz von Pestiziden schädigt die Umwelt; Pestizide sind ein Risiko für naturnahe Lebensräume; durch Pestizide wird die einheimische Fauna und Flora stark gefährdet; Pestizide beeinträchtigen Gewässerorganismen, wie Insektenlarven, Algen, Pilze und Fische; Pestizide verunreinigen Oberflächenwasser durch Abfluss von behandelten Pflanzen und Böden; es gibt eine zu hohe Konzentration von Düngemitteln und Pestiziden in den Wasserläufen; Pestizide und ihre Abbauprodukte verunreinigen das Grundwasser oft für Jahrzehnte; Insektizide und Fungizide reichern sich im Boden an mit negativen Effekten auf Bodenorganismen (z.B. Mykorrhiza-Pilze); der Einsatz von Pestiziden führt zu verringerter Bodenfruchtbarkeit; Verzicht auf Pestizide führt zu höherem Bodenverbrauch durch die Landwirtschaft; Einsatz von Herbiziden reduziert Vielfalt und Anzahl von Ackerwildpflanzen; Pestizide (Neonicotinoide) sind schuld am Bienensterben; Pestizide beeinflussen Vögel, Säugetiere und ihre Populationen direkt oder indirekt negativ; heute müssen wir feststellen, dass die Vögel aussterben; die intensive Landwirtschaft hat die Natur weitgehend vergiftet</i></p>
2	<p>Health consequences</p> <p><i>e.g., Insektizid ist für Kinder tödlich; PSM verursacht beim Ausbringer Vergiftungssymptome; Pestizide wirken sich negativ auf Spermienqualität aus; Die Verwendung von Pestiziden erhöht das Risiko im Alter an Parkinson zu erkranken; Umweltfaktoren, wie Pestizide, wirken sich immer stärker auf unsere Gesundheit aus; das Pilzbekämpfungsmittel ist als potenziell krebserregend eingestuft; Glyphosat hat krebserregende Eigenschaften; Verzicht auf Pestizide lässt Lebensmittel schneller verderben; in importierten Kräutern finden sich PSM-Rückstände; Pestizide verunreinigen Trinkwasser; Glyphosatrückstände im Getreide können bis zu 20 Teile pro Million erreichen; ohne Insektizide lässt sich Malaria nicht effektiv bekämpfen</i></p>
3	<p>Economic consequences</p> <p><i>e.g., ohne Pestizide können sich Landwirtschaftsbetriebe nicht effektiv vor Ernteaussfällen schützen; bei Verzicht auf Pestizide sinkt Ertrag pro Fläche; ein Verzicht auf Pestizide verunmöglicht den Anbau traditioneller Rebsorten; ohne Behandlungen gehen die Ernten regelmässig verloren; Erträge sind im Bioanbau durchschnittlich 20 % niedriger sind als bei konventionellen Kulturen; reduzieren wir den Einsatz von Pestiziden, ist ein Rückgang</i></p>

	<i>der Erträge aus der Rübenproduktion um 40 bis 50 Prozent zu erwarten; am Schluss bedeutet das höhere Preise für die Konsumenten; die Wettbewerbsfähigkeit der exportierenden Lebensmittelindustrie würde aufgrund der geringeren Möglichkeiten zur Beschaffung von Rohstoffen beeinträchtigt; durch Verzicht auf Pestizide erhöht sich der Aufwand und folglich auch die Kosten für die Landwirte; Landwirtschaftsbetriebe müssen bei einem Verzicht auf Pestizide zusätzliches Personal zur Unkrautbekämpfung einstellen; Verzicht auf Pestizide erhöht Lebensmittelpreise; Pestizidverbot gefährdet Arbeitsplätze im ländlichen Raum; ein Verzicht auf PSM verunmöglicht es, einen Selbstversorgungsgrad von 60 Prozent zu erreichen; ein Verbot wäre das das Ende des Rübenanbaus in der Schweiz; Verwendung von Pestiziden verursacht hohe externe Kosten, die von der Allgemeinheit getragen werden müssen; die Verwendung von Pestiziden führt zu nicht nachhaltigem Anbau und zur Abhängigkeit von wenigen Konzernen; durch frühes spritzen fördert man Resistenzen, welche den Rübenanbau künftig erschweren können</i>
4	General / unspecific consequences <i>e.g., ohne Pestizide geht es nicht; die Verwendung von Pestiziden hat zahlreiche negative Auswirkungen; die Pestizidrisiken</i>
99	Other consequences

Causes of the pesticide problem [PROB_CAU, num, man]

Please specify the causes of the pesticide problem emphasised the most by the speaker.

Question: What causes (or would cause) the problematic [use of pesticides / reduction of pesticide use] according to the speaker?

0	No causes mentioned
1	Political causes <i>e.g., angesichts des erklärten Ziels, den Einsatz von Pestiziden in der Landwirtschaft zu reduzieren, ist ein Rückgang der Erträge zu erwarten; ein Pestizidverbot gefährdet die Ernährungssicherheit; wir subventionieren unsere eigene Wasserverschmutzung; die Festlegung von Grenzwerten erfolgt in einem äusserst fragwürdigen Prozess; wir haben gute Gesetze, doch am Vollzug hapert es in den einzelnen Kantonen immer wieder</i>
2	Economic causes <i>e.g., Landwirte setzen Pestizide ein, um Ertragsausfälle zu verhindern; Treiber der auf hohe Produktion getrimmten Landwirtschaft sind Pestizid-hersteller und Futtermittel-Importeure; die Nachfrage nach Bio-Kartoffeln steigt nicht; Konsumenten legen die Latte bezüglich Produktqualität so hoch, dass diese mit der Natur allein oft nicht erreicht werden kann; aufgrund der wachsenden Bevölkerung musste immer mehr produziert werden</i>
3	Practical / technical causes <i>e.g., die Kulturen leiden dieses Jahr unter einem ausserordentlich hohen Befall von</i>

	<i>Blattläusen; auf der Kirschenplantage frass im Sommer eine Raupe viele Früchte an; es gibt immer schwarze Schafe in der Landwirtschaft; Rapsblüten sind sehr attraktiv für bestimmte Insekten, gegen die es nur wenige natürliche Lösungen gibt; es wäre zu schön, auch gegen das Syndrome Besses Richesses eine robuste Sorte zur Hand zu haben, aber das ist nicht der Fall; gespritzt wird nur, weil man nichts über die Langzeitfolgen weiss; Leute verwenden die Produkte in ihrem Garten, weil sie nichts über deren Giftigkeit wissen; leider sind gewisse wichtige Zusammenhänge in den Köpfen vieler Landwirte falsch gespeichert</i>
99	Other causes

Speaker position [PROB_POS, num, man]

Please specify the position the speaker takes on the pesticide problem, e.g., 2 (problem is denied) if an actor denies that the use of a particular pesticide causes chronic health problems.

Question: Does the speaker acknowledge/deny the pesticide problem described, i.e., the causal relationship of causes and consequences of [pesticide use / reducing pesticide use]?

1	Acknowledged as problem
2	Denied as problem
3	Ambivalent towards problem
4	Explicitly neutral towards problem
99	Unclear

Scope of the pesticide problem [PROB_SCOPE, num, man]

Please code the scope of the pesticide problem as mentioned by the speaker using the separate list of areas. The scope of the problem is **the area subject to the problem**. This includes its consequences and causes.

When, e.g., causes and consequences occur in different areas (e.g., pesticide contaminated during production in India, showing negative consequences only when used in Switzerland), we code the “aggregated” scope of both causes and consequences (e.g., global).

Normally, the problem scope is the country in which the problem occurs (tab “National”), e.g., 720 (Tanzania) if pesticides were found in the water well of a village in Tanzania. Exceptions are supra-, inter-, or transnational problems (e.g. problems caused by EU policies), where we code the supra-, inter-, or transnational area affected by the problem (tab “Regional”).

Code this variable also if no causes or consequences are mentioned, but when the scope is clear based on the context, e.g. 716 (Switzerland) when the document concentrates on Swiss politics. If the scope of a problem cannot be inferred, use code 999 (unclear).

Name of pesticide / plant protection product [PROB_PEST, txt]

If the speaker mentions one or more specific pesticides or plant protection products, please note down their names, e.g., *Glyphosat, DDT, Neonicotinoide*.

Name of culture [PROB_CULT, txt]

If the speaker mentions one or more specific cultures, please note down their names, e.g., *Äpfel, Trauben, Weizen*.

Solution

Solution to the pesticide problem [SOL_TYPE, num, man]

Please specify the type of solution the speaker mentions, i.e., whether or not it is a policy solution.

Policy solutions involve the introduction, repeal or revision of public policies, while **non-policy solutions** do not.

Typically non-policy solutions are about specific farming practices / technique or voluntary measures. If a speaker proposes specific farming practice / technique but wraps that into a call for political action, use code 1 (policy solution). If it is not clear whether it is a policy or non-policy solution (also not from the context), for general or unspecific calls for action, use code 4 (general unspecific). If a speaker mentions both policy and non-policy solutions, we code 1 (policy solution).

Question: What measures or actions are mentioned by the speaker as a solution to the pesticide problem?

0	No solution mentioned
1	Policy solution <i>e.g., es braucht eine Beschränkung des Pestizideinsatzes im Kanton Genf; vorgesehen ist ein Absenkpfad für den Einsatz von Pflanzenschutzmitteln; wir müssen den Einsatz von Giften begrenzen; Zulassungen sollten nur noch befristet ausgestellt werden dürfen; Ausnahme-bewilligungen gehören abgeschafft; die Prüfung von Gesuchen muss auf Basis der aktuellsten Erkenntnisse erfolgen; die Wirkung von Stoffen auf Ökosysteme / der Cocktail-Effekt sollte bei der Zulassung berücksichtigt werden; Hersteller müssen gezwungen werden, ihre Resultate mit den Behörden zu teilen; Spritzen mit Helikopter verbieten; es dürfen nur noch emissionsarme Spritzgeräte verwendet werden; in Zuströmbereichen dürfen keine PSM ausgebracht werden; rlaubte Grenzwerte müssen gesenkt werden; die Praxis bei der Erteilung und Überprüfung von Einfuhrtoleranzen muss angepasst werden; das Einhalten der Grenzwerte muss besser kontrolliert werden; bei der Reinigung von Maschinen muss künftig genauer hingeschaut werden; die Anzahl Messgrößen für die Überprüfung der Wirkstoffe muss von 20 auf 30 erhöht werden; eine Wirkstoffbuch-haltung bei Pestizidanwendern wäre nötig: Wer spritzt was, wie viel, wann, wo?; Neonicotinoide müssen verboten werden; wir dürfen die Verwendung von giftigen PSM nicht weiter erlauben; ein Pestizidverbot verursacht enorme Kosten; nur noch Betriebe, die pestizidfrei produzieren, dürfen Subventionen erhalten; mindestens ein</i>

	<i>normaler Mehrwertsteuersatz auf Pestizide wäre angebracht; es braucht mehr finanzielle Anreize für Bio / eine Reduktion des Pflanzenschutzmittel-Verbrauchs; Bauern müssen bei einer Umstellung ihres Betriebs finanziell unterstützt werden; Landwirte sollen einen Ressourceneffizienzbeitrag erhalten, wenn sie auf offener Ackerfläche auf Herbizide verzichten; es braucht die Unterstützung von Produktionssystemen, die auf den Einsatz von Pestiziden verzichten; es muss ein Mindestpreis im Gesetz verankert werden; es braucht nicht mehr, sondern weniger Vorschriften; ich bitte den Bundesrat, die Verwendung des Insektizids "Gaucho" vorübergehend wieder zu bewilligen</i>
2	Non-policy solution <i>e.g., anstatt PSM kann der Striegel eingesetzt werden; bei der Verwendung resistenter Sorten kann auf Pestizide weitestgehend verzichtet werden; die App hilft den Landwirten den Behandlungszeitpunkt genau zu bestimmen, wodurch sich die Menge an Pestiziden erheblich reduzieren lässt; Abnehmer landwirtschaftlicher Produkte sollten Ansprüche an Produkte senken; Konsumenten müssen sich ihrer Verantwortung bewusst werden; wir müssen Leute wählen, die sich gegen die Agrochemie zur Wehr setzen; der Handel muss bereit sein, Kompromisse einzugehen; Unkräuter können auch mechanisch entfernt werden; mit dem Einsatz von Drohnen können betroffene Pflanzen identifiziert und gezielt behandelt werden; die Verwendung neuester Injektordüsen reduziert das Driftrisiko erheblich; es braucht ein Label, das Konsumenten über verwendete PSM informiert; es braucht die Erforschung alternativer Methoden zum Schutz der Zuckerrüben, die Ermittlung toleranter Sorten und die Entwicklung von Warnmodellen zur gezielten Bekämpfung</i>
3	General / unspecific solution <i>e.g., etwas muss passieren; wir müssen endlich handeln; wir müssen den Einsatz von Pestiziden insgesamt reduzieren; die Mittel sollten gar nicht eingesetzt werden; es bleibt uns nur der Verzicht auf Pestizide; der Einsatz von Pestiziden muss in der Landwirtschaft massiv reduziert werden; die Agrarlobby muss gestoppt werden; wir brauchen mehr, nicht weniger biologische Landwirtschaft; mit Bio allein können wir die Welt nicht ernähren; die Konsumenten müssen besser über die ökologischen Auswirkungen der industriellen Landwirtschaft informiert werden; wir brauchen mehr Forschung</i>
99	Unclear

Filter: If SOL_TYPE ≠ 0

Speaker position [SOL_POS, num]

Please indicate whether the speaker is in favour or against the mentioned solution.

Question: Does the speaker support/oppose the described measures or actions?

1	Proposed as solution
2	Opposed as solution

3	Ambivalent towards solution
4	Explicitly neutral towards solution
99	Unclear

END OF FILTER: All cases

3.3 Actor attributes (Coding form: ACT_VARS)

For every actor occurring as **speaker** or **evidence source** in a given evidence-frame sequence, we code all identifying features (i.e., name, organization, function) mentioned in the text.

An actor can be an individual or a collective actor (e.g., government agency, company). **An actor must be identifiable by (1) its name (e.g., “Markus Ritter”), (2) its function (e.g., “Präsident des Bauernverbandes”), or (3) a description that clearly defines a group of individual or collective actors (e.g., “die Bauern,” “die Wissenschaft”).** The author of a document (e.g., journalist, politician) can also be an actor (esp. speaker), even if none of the above information is included in the text.

The same actor is sometimes referred to differently over the course of a document (e.g., name, function, pronoun). All features used for the identification of the same actor within a document are relevant for the coding of that actor. For example, we code the actor's function when its mentioned at the beginning of a document, but not within the evidence sequence.

In the case of collective actors, different individuals may speak on behalf of the collective within a document. In such cases, we code them as separate actors but understand the individuals as representatives of the collective and, accordingly, as one unit. For example, if three individuals speak on behalf of Greenpeace about the same pesticide problem, we consider this the same actor-frame sequence with the three individuals all coded as speakers in that sequence. However, if an individual puts forward a different position or problem than the collective she/he belongs to, we consider them two separate entities (i.e. code the statements as separate actor-frame sequences).

Also, actors sometimes form coalitions and co-appear within an evidence-frame sequence, e.g. as speakers: “Die Umweltverbände WWF und Pro Natura fordern einen Pestizidverzicht.” In such cases, as for individuals representing a collective, we code all actors as speaker of the same evidence sequence (same EFS_ID).

Document ID [DOC_ID, txt, man]

The DOC_ID of the document as described in the section on document level attributes above.

Evidence-frame sequence ID [EFS_ID, txt, man]

The ID of the evidence sequence must be attributed by the coder based on the evidence sequence's position in the text as an integer number (1, 2, 3, etc.). The Efs_ID for the first evidence sequence is 1, for the second 2, for the third 3, and so on.

If the same actor is speaker / evidence source in multiple evidence-frame sequences, you must code the actor only once by listing the relevant EFS_IDs as comma-separated list, e.g., 1, 2, 3.

Important: Make sure that you use the same EFS_ID for all codings related to the same evidence sequence (i.e., actors, evidence sequence). Otherwise, the coded information cannot be linked together.

Actor role [ACT_ROLE, num, man]

Specify whether an actor is **speaker** or **evidence source** in the evidence sequence. We do not code actors with any other roles, such as subjects (e.g., addressees, allies) or objects (e.g., victims).

For each evidence-frame sequence, at least one **speaker** must be coded. To qualify as a relevant speaker, an actor must bring up evidence in connection to a pesticide problem or a potential solution (see introduction to section 3 above). The speaker does not have to agree with the evidence referred to, but can also be indifferent, adverse or neutral towards it (see EV_VAL).

For political documents, we only code the author of the document (i.e., MP or Federal Council/department) as speaker. In mass and trade media articles, speakers can also be actors who are given a platform in the article by the author. To decide between author and another actor as speaker, use the following flowchart.

In general, the speaker role is active in the sense that the actor can speak for her/himself. Typically, this is indicated by direct or indirect speech, e.g., "actor XY states/warns/requests...". Furthermore, the main function of the quotation should not be providing support for the author's argument. What is decisive therefore is not who presents the evidence (e.g., results of a study), but who is responsible for the inclusion of the evidence in the text. For example, we would code the IARC as speaker in the following statement: "*Triclosan ist ein potenzielles Karizonogen. Dies stelle das IARC in einer Studie fest.*" For the following statement, on the other hand, we would code the author of the document as speaker: "*Triclosan ist ein potenzielles Karizonogen. Dies stelle auch das IARC in einer Studie fest.*"

Figure 6. Identification of speaker in media documents.

The **evidence source**, on the other hand, is the actor who produced the factual data or information that is used as evidence. The role of the evidence source is thus passive in the sense that the actor is referred to. A passive role is characterized by phrases like “...according to the findings of a study by actor YZ”. To identify the evidence source, you may ask yourself: **Who produced the factual data or information that is used as evidence in the text?**

Within an evidence sequence, the same actor can be both speaker and evidence source, namely if a speaker uses evidence that she/he has produced her/himself, e.g. if she/he refers to personal experience or own measurements. This is also true for statements that we identify as evidence sequence only because of the actor type of the speaker (i.e., science actor). In this case, we code the same actor as both speaker and evidence source.

1	Speaker Actor who brings up evidence in connection to a pesticide problem or a potential solution
2	Evidence source Actor who produced the factual data or information used as evidence

Family name of the actor [ACT_FAMNAME, txt]

Please note down the family name of the actor without any titles (e.g., “Dr.,” “Prof.”). If only an organization (e.g., project team, NGO, government department, company) is mentioned but no individual, we only code ACT_ORG. If multiple individuals are named who all belong to the same organisation and all put forward the organization's position, we also code ACT_ORG only.

Given name of the actor [ACT_GIVNAME, txt]

When mentioned in the text, please write down the first name(s) of the actor.

Organization name of the actor [ACT_ORGANAME, txt]

When mentioned, please write down the name of the institution, organization, company, party, newspaper etc. the actor is associated with, i.e. acting on its behalf. Also code this variable if only the organization's name is provided and if several individuals represent the same organization.

If an individual is associated with several organizations, we only code the first one mentioned.

Before writing down an organization's name, check the actor list whether we have already identified the organization as an actor before. If so, please use the notation used in the actor list. If the organization's name is not yet on the actor list, please add it to the list.

When adding a Swiss organisation to the actor list, check [Zefix](#) (Central Business Name Index) first and then, if necessary, check the organization's own website for the organisation's official name in both French and German.

Description of the actor [ACT_DESC, txt]

Use ACT_DESC if additional information on the function of an actor is provided (e.g., “Projektleiter,” “Präsidentin”), if only the function of the speaker is mentioned (e.g., “die

Bundespräsidentin,” “der Wissenschaftler”), or if actors are referred to by aliases (e.g., Twitter handles, user names in online forums). Use this category also if only a description of group of individual or collective actors is given (e.g., “die Bauern,” “die Wissenschaft”). Always code this variable when a description is given.

Actor type [ACT_TYPE, num, man]

(Rucht et al., 2008; Schmid-Petri et al., 2013; Waldherr et al., 2015)

For each actor, we code the actor type. If an actor can fall into different categories depending on context and role mentioned in a document, we code the code the type mentioned first, e.g., 231 (farmer) for *Biowinzer und Mitinitiant Julien Amand*.

All categories cover organizations and institutions, as well as unorganized collectives and individuals, e.g., “die Konsumenten” should be coded as 37 (Consumer organisation/group).

If the description of an actor is too unspecific to code a subcategory, code the main category, e.g., an unspecified politician, where it is unclear whether she/he is referred to as government, parliament or party representative, is coded as 10 (Political actor).

Exception: If only the name of an organisation is mentioned and the category is not clear from it (e.g., Vision Landwirtschaft), the name should be googled. Short descriptions can usually be found on the "about us" page on the organisation's website or, in case of Swiss organisations, on the [Lobbywatch website](#).

If scientific studies are cited but no specific author of the study is mentioned, we code 351 (Scientific, research professional/institution).

If a scientist/researcher is employed at a political institution and directly works for them, she/he is coded as political actor. The same applies if a scientist/researcher works for a media organisation (e.g., a meteorologist) who is responsible for the presentation of weather forecasts. She/he is coded as 40 (Media actor), not as expert/scientist.

10	Political actor	
	11	Government / executive Government and government representatives, e.g., <i>Bundesrat Parmelin; der Bundesrat; Regierungsrat; Bundesratssprecher André Simonazzi; Kommission der Europäischen Union; Gemeindepräsidentin; Konferenz der Kantonsregierungen; Konferenz der kantonalen Landwirtschaftsdirektoren (LDK)</i>
	12	Administration / state executive agency <i>e.g., Eidgenössisches Departement für Wirtschaft, Bildung und Forschung (WBF); Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft (BLW); Amt für Abfall, Wasser, Energie und Luft; WHO; FAO; Eidgenössische Kommission für Konsumentenfragen; European Food Safety Authority (EFSA); Konferenz der kantonalen Pflanzenschutzdienste (KPSD); Vereinigung der kantonalen Fachleute für Gewässerbiologie und -chemie (Cercl'eau); Kantonale Fachstellen; also the general terms “die Behörden” or</i>

		“Agenturen” (e.g., “Risikobewertungsagentur”)
13	Legislative	Legislatives and parliaments, including individual members, parliamentary groups, and committees, e.g., <i>Nationalrat; Ständerat; Kommission für Umwelt, Raumplanung und Energie (UREK); NR Lisa Mazzone; Mitte Fraktion; Kantonsrat; Europäisches Parlament</i>
14	Political party	Political parties, party representatives, working groups, intra-party groups, youth parties, e.g., <i>GLP-Präsident Grossen; Delegiertenversammlung der SVP; Juso; FDP-Frauen; Mitglieder der Christlich-Demokratischen Partei</i>
15	Direct-democratic, initiative / referendum committee	<i>e.g., Initiatin Franziska Herren; Verein Sauberes Wasser für alle; Vereinigung für eine Schweiz ohne synthetische Pestizide (LebenstattGift); die Initiantinnen und Initianten</i>
16	Judiciary	Courts, judges, prosecutors, e.g., <i>Bundesverwaltungsgericht</i>
17	Police, internal security agency, military	<i>e.g., Kantonspolizei; Grenzschutz; Armee; Nachrichtendienst</i>
18	Central bank	<i>e.g., Nationalbank; IWF; Weltbank</i>
19	Whole political body	Countries, whole economies, federal states, local communities, e.g., <i>Schweiz; Aargau; EU; westliche Demokratien; der Bund</i>
20	Economic actor	
21	Employers' association, trade and professional association	<i>e.g., Schweizer Bauernverband (SBV); Schweizerischer Getreideproduzentenverband (SGPV); Vereinigung schweizerischer biologischer Landbauorganisationen (BioSuisse); Schweizer Wirtschaftsverband Chemie, Pharma, und Life Science (scienceindustries); Verband der Waldeigentümer (WaldSchweiz); Schweizerischer Saatgutproduzenten-Verband (Swissem); Interessensgemeinschaft Agrarstandort Schweiz (IGAS); JardinSuisse; Dachverband der Schweizerischen Bienenzüchtervereine (apisuisse); Schweizerischer Fischerei-Verband (SFV-FSP)</i>
22	Union, workers' association	<i>e.g., Unia, Schweizerischer Gewerkschaftsbund (SGB); Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Berufsverbände landwirtschaftlicher Angestellter (ABLA); Travail.Suisse; Uniterre; also general terms like “Arbeiter” and “Angestellte”</i>

	23	Company	
		231	Farmer Individual farmers, also general terms, <i>e.g., Bauer, Landwirte, Imker</i>
		232	Input supplier Agricultural companies, such as <i>Fenaco Genossenschaft (fenaco); Saatzucht Düdingen; UFA AG, Landi Schweiz AG</i> , as well as agrochemical company, such as <i>Syngenta; Bayer-Monsanto; Dow Chemical</i>
		233	Health company Hospitals, health insurance companies, care facilities
		234	Food company <i>e.g., Nestlé, JOWA; Unilever</i> ; also gastronomy (restaurants, catering)
		235	Retailer <i>e.g., Coop, Migros, Lidl</i>
		236	Public infrastructure provider Providers of, <i>e.g., water supply, electricity networks, waste disposal</i>
30	Non-profit actor of civil society		
	31	Environmental movement / organization / group <i>e.g., Pro Natura, WWF Schweiz, BirdLife Schweiz; Stiftung Landschaftsschutz Schweiz (SL); Aqua Viva; Ärztinnen und Ärzte für Umweltschutz</i> ; also general terms like “Umweltschützer”	
	32	Food movement / organization / group <i>e.g., Swissveg, Slow Food; Schweizer Allianz Gentechfrei (SAG)</i>	
	33	Health association / organization / group <i>e.g., Krebsliga, Parkinson Schweiz</i> ; also general terms like “Allergiker”	
	34	Solidarity, human rights, peace, welfare movement / organization / group <i>e.g., Amnesty International (AI), Terre des Hommes (Tdh), Médecins sans frontières (MSF), Alliance Sud, Public Eye, Gesellschaft für bedrohte Völker (GfbV), Fastenopfer, Schweizerisches Rotes Kreuz (SRK)</i>	
	35	Expert / scientist Actors with specific expertise, <i>e.g., think tanks (Avenir Suisse)</i>	
		351	Scientific professional / institution Research institutes, universities, scientific associations, <i>e.g., Eawag, Agroscope, Universität Bern, Scientists for Future, Elinor Ostrom</i> . Also general terms like “die Wissenschaftler” or “die Forschung”
		352	Health expert Doctors, nurses, etc. that are not research professionals

	353	Agricultural expert Consulting organisations and schools that are not research professional, e.g., <i>BeratungsForum Schweiz; Schweizerische Vereinigung für die Entwicklung der Landwirtschaft und des Ländlichen Raums AGRIDEA, Strickhof, Landwirtschaftliches Zentrum SG; Vision Landwirtschaft (VL), Apiservice</i>
	36	Church, religious organization
	37	Consumer organization / group <i>e.g., Konsumentenforum (KF), Stiftung für Konsumentenschutz (SKS);</i> also general terms like “die Konsumenten” oder “die Haushalte”
	38	Other civil society organization / group Groups formed by members who share a common trait or attribute, including not already mentioned social categories, e.g., <i>Jugend, Kleinkinder, Alte, Familien, Arbeitslose, indigene Bevölkerung, ethnische Minderheit, besonders sensible Menschen, empfindliche Bevölkerungsgruppen</i>
40		Media Including online/offline media, trade media, film-makers, individual journalists, etc.
50		The public
	51	Single private person / citizen Random persons as representatives of a population, ordinary authors of letters to the editor, persons on the street, in the supermarket, etc.
	52	General public <i>e.g., die Öffentlichkeit; die Steuerzahler; die Stimmbürger; zukünftige Generationen; Herr und Frau Schweizer; der Mensch</i>
99		Other actor <i>e.g. selbsternannte Schädlingsexperten</i>

FILTER: If ACT_TYPE ∈ {11, 13, 14}

Party affiliation [ACT_PARTY, num]

(Schmid-Petri et al., 2013; Waldherr et al., 2015)

We code the party affiliation of an actor, if it is explicitly mentioned in the text. Otherwise just leave this variable blank.

We code the youth parties in the same category as their parent party (e.g., Juso as SP) and predecessor parties in the category of their respective successors (e.g., CVP as Mitte).

1	Schweizerische Volkspartei (SVP)
2	Sozialdemokratische Partei (SP)

3	FDP.Die Liberalen (FDP)
4	Die Mitte (Christlichdemokratische Volkspartei CVP, Bürgerlich-Demokratische Partei BDP)
5	Grüne
6	Grünliberale Partei (GLP)
7	Other

END OF FILTER: All cases

Actor scope [ACT_SCOPE, num, man]

Please code the actor's scope using the separate list of areas. Normally, the actor scope is the actor's country of residence / the actor's domicile (tab "National"). Exceptions are supra-, inter-, or transnational actors (e.g. international organisations or political bodies), where we code the supra-, inter-, or transnational area the actor is linked to (tab "Regional").

Always code the scope of the actors as mentioned in the text, that is 716 (Switzerland) for *Schweizer Unternehmen* also when the actor addresses a problem with a different scope in the given actor-frame sequence. For multinationals, code the country in which they are active according to the matter discussed in the document (e.g., USA for Bayer if the document is about a lawsuit in the USA).

Code this variable also if no scope is mentioned, but when the scope is clear based on the context given by the document (e.g., 716 (Switzerland) for a member of the Swiss parliament or for a journalist publishing in a Swiss newspaper). If the scope of an actor cannot be inferred, use code 999 (unclear).

Position vis-à-vis the popular initiatives on pesticide-free farming

If an actor is attributed a clear position vis-a-vis at least one of the two popular initiatives, we code this information. If the position is not clear from the text, leave the variable blank.

In cases where a change of position is implied/considered in the future (e.g., in case of a "Gegenvorschlag"), we code the current position of the actor at the time of the statement made in the document.

1	Proponent of the initiative
2	Opponent of the initiative
3	Explicitly neutral towards the initiative

<i>List of initiatives</i>
Trinkwasserinitiative [ACT_VOTE_WATER]
Pestizidinitiative [ACT_VOTE_PEST]

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